

UK “multi-PID consortium” business case

Prepared for the UK PIDs for Open Access to UK Research (“PIDs for OA”) project Consortium Task Group by Josh Brown and Alice Meadows (consultants, MoreBrains Cooperative), November 2020 and revised January 2021.

1. Introduction

The benefits of widespread PID adoption have been established as including better workflows and automation for researchers, funders, research organizations, and end-users. Widespread PID adoption also promises much richer data on research activities and processes, with widespread benefits for all stakeholders in the form of new insights into research activities and processes, which will help identify 'what works?' and lead to opportunities for improvements and efficiencies. Technical development of leading candidate PIDs has reached maturity, but community adoption has been slow.

A new approach is therefore needed to lower the financial, technical, organizational, and human barriers to wider adoption of PIDs. The 2019 PID Roadmap for open access to UK research report¹ recommended forming a ‘multi-PID consortium’ to optimise access and adoption of five priority PIDs for open research. (See Appendix 1 below for the detailed rationale for this recommendation.)

The vision set out in the proposal for a ‘multi-PID’ consortium is primarily concerned with convening and supporting PID adoption in the UK research community. Subsequent research² undertaken as part of the PIDs for OA project, which followed the original report, confirmed that technical and financial barriers to adoption are too high, existing PID adoption is seen as underdelivering on expected benefits, and integrations are often partial and slow to arrive.

PID adoption across the five priority PIDs will need to ramp up dramatically and comprehensively in order to realise the network benefits that the community wishes to see (improved efficiencies in all aspects of research information management, enhanced interoperability between internal and external systems alike, etc.).

While progress has been made, challenges remain, and these should not be underestimated. For example, 80% of research information systems surveyed are not using ROR IDs for organisations. 25% of ORCID UK consortium members still do not have a live integration more than five years after the consortium was formed; and, where they do exist, many integrations are not yet adding information to researchers’ ORCID records. While 120 UK institutions have access to DataCite DOIs, relatively few are leveraging the potential of

¹ Brown, Josh (2020) Developing a persistent identifier roadmap for open access to UK research. Available at: <http://repository.jisc.ac.uk/7840/>

² Brown, Josh and Meadows, Alice (2020) *Persistent identifiers adoption and awareness survey report*. Available at: <https://repository.jisc.ac.uk/8107/>

this for OA-critical outputs such as author accepted manuscripts. Grant IDs and RAIDs for projects have zero, or close to zero, adoption.

How can a multi-PID consortium generate the levels of PID coverage that are needed for increased openness for UK research and reduced administrative burden for our researchers?

Firstly, the consortium must be designed to ensure the sustainability of the PIDs and PID services it facilitates access to. Consortial membership models (such as that offered by ORCID) are designed to lower the price of PID services, which are set as low as they can be without harming the ability of PID providers to continue to function. Consortial memberships can also be used to 'rebalance' costs across a community, ensuring that there is equitable access to membership of a PID service irrespective of an organisation's size or financial resources.

Secondly, the consortium should be built to meet the challenges of PID integration across the UK research and innovation sector. Membership of a PID consortium alone does not guarantee the ability to make effective use of that PID service. Many organisations lack either systems that can interact with PID services or the capability to build integrations on their own. Others may have this expertise in-house without knowing that they have access to it. System vendors face competing demands for new features, and some see a strategic threat in increasing the openness of the data in their systems.

A centralised mechanism for invoicing and administration of the consortium could be an efficient way to handle membership processes across different PID organisations. However, a much greater challenge is ensuring that the potential benefits of the priority PIDs are delivered in a reasonable timeframe. Quick wins are needed to demonstrate this potential, but longer term, deeper integrations must follow if these benefits are to be realised equitably and at scale. This will require ongoing, stable support for community coordination and practical integrations. A consortial approach to multi-PID adoption could help to address all these challenges.

2. Context

This document is intended to explore the potential business case for a UK multi-PID consortium. This consortium would be a critical corollary to the proposed UK "Research Identifier National Coordinating Council" (RINCC), which was approved at the September 2020 meeting of the PIDs for OA project stakeholder group meeting.

While the RINCC is intended to develop long-term strategic and policy engagement between key groups within the UK research and innovation sector (including senior leaders) and the global PID community, the consortium would be a more operationally-focused initiative. The RINCC will focus on governance and community accountability, while the consortium would be designed to maximise access to, and the utility of, priority PID services both in the UK and in the international systems upon which UK research communication depends.

The primary focus of the consortium would be community support and liaison, to address the practical issues of increasing coverage (such as making sure AAMs in repositories have a DOI and a link to funding) and supporting integrations in critical funding, research management, and publication systems. The consortium, as envisaged, could also play a central role in ensuring access to PID services for all who need them in the UK research and innovation sector. This could be achieved by rebalancing costs, to lower barriers to membership for smaller or poorer institutions; by seeking economies of scale in the national support network; and potentially by securing funding to accelerate adoption or to secure comprehensive participation.

The need for a focus on adoption and integration is borne out by the landscape analyses undertaken in the Developing a persistent Identifier roadmap for open access to UK research and the subsequent survey (both cited above). Figure 1 (below) gives an indication of where each PID currently sits in terms of adoption.

Figure 1: UK research community priority PID adoption curve

This document contains an analysis of the business model for the potential PID consortium. It has been developed at the request of the consortium task group, to help inform their discussion of the viability of the proposed consortium. It also provides a summary of the group’s considerations and context for any recommendations the task group makes to the main project stakeholder group and, subsequently, the RINCC.

3. Considerations

The preliminary questionnaire shared with the consortium task group in preparation for their first meeting set out a very clear set of benefits and risks in the consortium approach (summarised in the slides from the meeting which are available [here](#)). However, this analysis focuses more on the essential rationale for the consortium model.

The fundamental goal of this consortium proposal is to create a sustainable mechanism for boosting the integration and adoption of the five priority PIDs (Crossref and DataCite DOIs,

ORCID iDs, RAiD and ROR identifiers) across the research and innovation sector, by focusing on long-term practical support and advocacy. We have identified the potential customers and sought to evaluate the return on investment for the different stakeholder groups participating in the consortium.

We have also set out the key use cases for members, although use cases for the consortium overlap significantly with use cases for the PIDs themselves. Since the goal of the consortium is to maximise access to and adoption of PID services, success would largely be manifest in the realisation of the benefits of PIDs.

In framing our analysis, we have kept in mind several key factors which were raised in the first task group meeting.

Firstly, the consortium model is not intended to leverage collective buying power, for example, to drive down the price of PID services. The PIDs under consideration are community-led, not-for-profit organisations with explicit goals to support the wider open research infrastructure. They operate transparently and on a cost recovery basis, so any ambition to lower their fees would be actively counter-productive. We therefore recommend that one of the consortium 'must haves' is a sustainability guarantee, ideally to be included in any terms of reference or founding framework for the initiative.

Monitoring potential unintended consequences should be a key role for the RINCC. As the PID landscape evolves, the RINCC should continue to evaluate the sustainability or viability of 'priority PIDs' to ensure that the UK research and innovation sector can be confident that the PID services they invest in and deploy will persist.

The consortium should focus on extending more support for PID adoption and integration, and on containing the cost of that extra support. Whatever the costs may be (and these will need to be modelled in detail), they must not exceed the perceived or actual value of the enhanced PID network and services that will arise from this investment.

As well as containing costs, the consortium should be concerned with balancing costs across the UK research and innovation sector, to avoid excluding participants, or reinforcing the Matthew effect of accumulated advantage. This is a real risk if only the larger, already successful research-intensive organisations can afford to leverage the benefits of PIDs. To manage this risk, subsequent analyses will need to consider a range of options to rebalance costs whilst maintaining sustainable revenue levels for PID providers, such as price banding across consortium members, or subsidies.

The consortium will need to be flexible, extensible to encompass more PIDs as needed, and able to offer an adaptable menu suited to the needs of a varied constituency. Participation must not require subscribing to services that members either do not need or have the capacity to use. At the same time, the group may wish to consider the possibility of building in mechanisms to incentivise greater PID adoption amongst members. One group member drew an analogy to financial services/banks: not everyone wants all the services on offer at a bank, but everyone can be a customer.

With these assumptions and framing considerations in mind, we have focussed our analysis on the business case, composition, and potential benefits of a multi-PID consortium for the UK.

4. Consortium business model analysis

This analysis is based on the Business Model Canvas approach, which sets out the key activities, purpose, and components of a business activity. The Canvas is designed to present a simplified version of the consortium, which enables us to identify its core activities and constituencies. If these are identified correctly at this initial stage, stakeholder specific issues can be operationalised within this framework during implementation.

The first step in creating the Canvas is to break down the consortium membership into distinct customer segments, each of which has a context for their need for PIDs. This allows us to establish the core, cross-cutting value proposition for each function that the consortium could support.³

4.1. The UK PID consortium Business Model Canvas

We now present the complete Business Model Canvas for the proposed UK PID consortium, broken down by section, with an accompanying magnified image of the relevant panel. For an overview of the whole Canvas, see Figure 2 (below); high resolution copies of the image are available to accompany this report.

Figure 2: The UK PID consortium Business Model Canvas

NB: This image is available in high resolution [JPEG](#) and [PDF](#) for ease of viewing

To help track themes across the Canvas and aid the interpretation of the individual panels, we have colour coded the ‘sticky notes’ as follows:

³ “A value proposition is a promise of value to be delivered, communicated, and acknowledged. It is also a belief from the customer about how value (benefit) will be delivered, experienced and acquired. A value proposition can apply to an entire organization, or parts thereof, or customer accounts, or products or services.” https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Value_proposition

Business model canvas legend

4.1.1. Value propositions

These high-level value propositions encapsulate each customer segment’s need for PIDs, representing the essence of the main problem they need to solve. Cutting across all stakeholder groups is the overarching PID value proposition of efficiency gains in all tasks and activities involving the use of research information. The consortium proposal is the most effective way to deliver all the value propositions set out here.

Figure 3: Value propositions

4.1.2. Critical use cases

In response to a specific request made at the first consortium task group meeting, we have also incorporated key use cases for each customer segment identified during the project into our analysis.

We have identified several use cases that cut across groups, reinforcing the core value propositions for PIDs themselves. These include enhancing interoperability and data re-use across internal and external systems; reductions in administrative burden, cutting overhead and potentially releasing expertise and resources for higher value activities; and enhancing data quality, with consequent benefits for assessment, analysis, and decision support. These will be valuable, alongside the top-level value propositions, in developing messaging and engagement programmes to support increased adoption and awareness of PIDs.

Figure 4: critical use cases

The use cases for funders may not apply equally to all, but every funder should recognise at least one, if not several, of these needs.

Institutional use cases cut across the various professional communities (for example career tracking is more likely to be a need for the research office, whereas discoverability of outputs fits the library mission) but they all speak to core strategic needs for most research-performing organisations. We note that the applicability and priority of these use cases may vary between large and small, or between research- or teaching-intensive organisations.

For content platforms, the use cases speak to lower overheads as well as enhanced service opportunities. They will also impact other customer segments: new content metrics could provide enhanced career tracking or business intelligence for institutions and could help to accelerate a more responsible evaluation environment.

Use cases for researchers go beyond the core benefits of reduced burden, to include new opportunities for research on research, enhanced discovery, and new potential career paths.

4.1.3. Customer segments

We have identified four primary customer segments for the potential UK PID consortium, distinguished by their functional roles.

Figure 5: Customer segments

Funders would (primarily but not exclusively) register grant IDs and actively maintain the metadata associated with these. They would be high-volume consumers of PIDs and related metadata. In this context, the UK Government could be a funder, or could be represented and served by publicly supported funders such as UKRI.

Institutions play a pivotal role in supporting researchers and research. They would interact heavily with ORCID records, and would be primary registrants of RAIDs for projects. Specific use cases (such as those of librarians and research managers) are subsumed in this segment, as one institutional membership could cover the needs of all professional groups within the institution. They may also need to register grant IDs.

Content services include both repositories and publishers. Their primary roles are registering DOIs for content, and providing and maintaining output metadata.

Researchers are, as indicated, not direct customers of the consortium, but are included as a distinct segment because their needs and experiences are crucial drivers of participation for the other segments. Given the value of PID

metadata in evidencing professional progression and achievements, this group may also include student researchers, linking teaching and research activities to career pathways.

It is worth noting that a single organisation could be assigned to more than one 'segment', for example, the Royal Society is both a funder and a publisher ('content services'), and it

also represents researchers. While each of the top-level associated value propositions apply, there are likely to be specific interplays between them that could be explored in future work.

Eligibility criteria will need to be carefully considered for groups outside academic organisations, for example, to take account of for-profit players and the global nature of research, and also to account for 'academe-adjacent' industries such as pharmaceuticals, engineering, and others with a major 'R&D' component. The task group recommends that options for these criteria should be assessed as part of the consortium development process.

4.1.4. Channels

A channel is the means by which a product reaches customers. Many customers will have interactions across channels, as when institutions obtain DataCite membership and user support via the British Library, but their local integration is provided by a system vendor. There is significant overlap in the memberships of the existing ORCID and DataCite UK consortia. Not every channel will be applicable to every customer, and there are some channels (such as ROR or RAiD ‘membership’) which are still under development.

Figure 6: Channels

The existing consortium leads (such as the British Library for the DataCite consortium or Jisc for the ORCID consortium) represent a channel, as they provide access to and support for PIDs.

Crossref ‘sponsoring organisations’ represent another existing channel. They usually provide considerable support for the organisations that participate in their sponsorship arrangement.

We have also classified system and platform providers as a channel for PID services, as they are frequently the route by which PID services are

accessed. Their intermediary role is critical for adoption purposes, as they can act as effective gatekeepers. By integrating or not integrating PIDs, they determine access to them for their entire customer base.

The existing consortial frameworks (Crossref’s sponsorship system, and the DataCite and ORCID membership consortia) have arisen organically through community demand. Extending these frameworks with an additional support layer requires a conscious design decision about how the consortium might reinforce these networks or engender new ones. We note that this decision should be based on careful evaluation and consultation with existing and new customers, as well as with the PID providing organisations.

4.1.5. Customer relationships

Customer relationships are distinct from channels, and describe the relationships between the consortium and its members that are needed for it to function effectively. These are categorised as intrinsic to the consortium and will incur costs.

Figure 7: Customer relationships

Customer support will be a critical relationship for the consortium, driving much of its visibility, and playing a vital role in enabling the realisation of PID integrations and benefits.

Community groups (whether for specific PIDs or for professional segments or communities of practice) will be needed to enable the consortium to understand evolving sector needs and gather evidence to support interventions. Various PID providers and consortium leads have developed self-service portals to enable members to manage their own data, and to configure their PID integrations. These will need to be

developed, expanded, and updated over time.

4.1.6. Key activities

Key activities are implied or required by the value propositions. These processes are considered vital for the consortium to operate successfully, so understanding the nature and scale of these activities is crucial to developing a realistic costing for the consortium.

Figure 8: key activities

We have broken the activities into three thematic areas, represented by the clustering of sticky notes in the Canvas.

Communications-related activities include community coordination and outreach across the UK. Additional roles, which should be agreed in partnership with the PID providers' communications experts, could include developing messaging around benefits and on the top-level value propositions for PIDs in general.

Administrative functions that are essential to the effective operation of the consortium include: procurement and licensing for PID services, and potentially for support functions;

member management; and invoicing for memberships and services. The consortium will also need to offer its own customer support and build up self-service portals to help to contain overheads.

Technical coordination will be critical to successful adoption, and to ensuring that community feedback can be synthesised and used to inform product development for PID providers. Activities that fall within this category include: participating in the development of standards; supporting schema or taxonomy development (including mappings and crosswalks to boost interoperability between the priority PID systems); and producing documentation to support integration and adoption amongst member organisations.

4.1.7. Key partners

Key partners are external organisations or groups that are essential to the successful delivery of the key activities and value propositions. They may include consortium members, organisations leading similar initiatives from other countries, and community groups or service providers essential to the delivery of PIDs and services to their users. The task group notes that there are stakeholders not present as ‘key partners’ whose priorities or goals could affect the success of the consortium. A wider stakeholder analysis should therefore be considered.

Figure 9: Key partners

PID providers are critical to the success of the consortium, not just in terms of offering the core infrastructures that make up the *raison d’être* for the consortium, but because without their buy-in and support, the consortium will not be viable.

Funders are essential to the mission of the consortium, especially in terms of potential support for ensuring equitable access to consortium membership and participation. With resources and policy tools (including mandates if appropriate) at their disposal, funders can shape the landscape for the PID consortium.

Sector and professional groups will be essential to both understanding the needs and evolving priorities of the research and innovation sector, and driving awareness and adoption of PID services.

Institutions are key members of the potential consortium community and have the capacity to drive sustained changes in research practice, for example, normalising the use of ORCID IDs across research activities, and educating researchers and contributors in the value of PIDs.

System/platform vendors are, as noted throughout this analysis, fundamental to the delivery and usability of PID

services.

Related initiatives (which include similar national-level organisations and international networks) will be vital for aligning the consortium's work with wider research goals and for maintaining the UK's place in the international networks of both PIDs for research and research itself.

Finally, publishing groups, such as industry associations, will play a pivotal role in delivering the benefits of PIDs. If funders register grant IDs, and institutions are populating researchers' ORCID records with useful data, registering RAIDs, and providing reliable links to data and other associated materials, these all need to be embedded in outputs consistently and accurately. This, in turn, will enable the reporting, analysis, indexing, impact evaluation, and other functions sought by consortium stakeholders.

Beyond the consortium partnerships, the RINCC will have a crucial role to play in developing strategic alliances, prioritising economies of scale, mitigating risks, and aligning policies to both leverage and bolster increased PID adoption.

4.1.8. Key resources

These resources are required by the value propositions for the consortium. Some are already in place (such as national PID support hubs at the British Library and Jisc), while others are being established as part of the PID roadmap project (such as the RINCC).

Figure 10: Key resources

PID support hubs will need to be extended, reinforced, and coordinated effectively by the consortium. There is real depth of expertise and community relationships in the existing hubs, so any development must ensure there is no risk of undermining or duplicating them.

User groups and communities of practice are an effective way to influence product development, understand community needs, and share experience and knowledge.

The RINCC will provide the policy and governance context for the consortium, as well as a venue for assessing the delivery of the value propositions, and

the sustainability of the consortium and the wider PID network. It will also have to assess the 'ownership' of these resources and make sure that key partnerships include the movers behind existing networks or initiatives.

Critically, without a range of forms of support from Jisc and UKRI (including but not limited to political, financial, and convening), the consortium will not progress. For this reason, we have classified these resources as integral to the consortium itself. It is hard to see momentum and engagement reaching credible levels without their medium- to long-term support.

5. Proposed next steps

The UK PIDs for open access roadmap project has five major strategic areas of investigation:

1. National coordination of PID-related activities
2. The sustainability of the priority PID providers
3. Improved PID integrations
4. Benefits realisation for existing and emerging PIDs
5. A national PID consortium

The project hypothesis is that, for the benefits of PID adoption to be realised, there need to be significantly higher levels of integration between organisational systems and open PID infrastructures, with functionality to enable two way flows of metadata wherever possible. With consistent, widespread integrations, levels of technical interoperability would increase, offering improved data re-use and quality, enhanced automation, and significant efficiency savings.

To deliver these efficiencies, we need people with technical and community expertise, dedicated to providing rigorous and robust technical support for new and existing PID integrations. The value of the consortial approach outlined above is that it would provide a framework to deliver this type of support for every research organisation in the UK, maximising returns on a national investment in PIDs.

The consortium will provide the means to operationalise the core PID strategy, while the Research Identifier National Coordinating Committee (RINCC) will provide strategic oversight and liaise with senior stakeholders. However, the RINCC alone will not be able to drive up integration and adoption levels. The question is: will the benefits of that adoption justify the costs of the consortium? The answer to this should be provided by a rigorous cost-benefit analysis.

The analysis should gather data on the current UK-wide research information flows indicated by the value propositions, and compare them with examples of highly automated PID-optimised workflows from around the world (such as the work that has already been undertaken in Portugal and Australia⁴). In costing the real-world time savings from these examples and scaling them to match the volume of UK research information, it will be possible to model the benefits of varying levels of PID integration. Cost modelling would cover memberships and the levels of support needed to achieve those levels of integration, thus building the business case for investments in adoption support.

This work can then be used to create measures of success and an endpoint for the consortium programme. The RINCC would play a steering role, including updating targets, assessing progress, and deciding when returns on investment in PIDs have reached a self-sustaining level.

⁴ Specifically the Australian Research Council's integration of ORCID in their grant application system, and the PT-CRIS national information sync framework.

If the cost-benefit analysis indicates that a PID support consortium could help the UK research and innovation sector become more efficient, the consortium task group has identified a number of additional questions that may subsequently need to be explored.

These include:

- Alignment of overlapping stakeholder groups: create a unified stakeholder mapping for the consortium alongside the RINCC
- Identify and mitigate any potential impacts on existing PID consortia and PID providers
- Explore consortium membership criteria and limits. Could commercial or international entities join the consortium? Should it be limited to not-for-profits that are based in and/or primarily serve the UK? Would all not-for-profits be eligible (e.g. OUP, CUP)?
- Consult with the community to validate the initial value propositions identified for PIDs and the consortium itself
- Expand and refine the use cases which have been identified so far in the context of priority workflows
- Are there any changes in the wider environment we need to consider? Do they relate to culture, policy or technology?
- Can we establish a roadmap of how the consortium can scale up or be phased across sectors - can this expand to industry, impact, societal, or policy goals etc?
- What are the value propositions for governmental stakeholders, and how do they relate to those for funders and institutions?

Appendix 1: The original consortium proposal

The PID Roadmap for open access to UK research report⁵ recommended that the UK community explore the potential for a ‘multi-PID consortium’ to optimise access and adoption of the five priority PIDs for open research. The report set out the following rationale:

“The UK ORCID consortium has demonstrated the power of leveraging consortial communities... There has been very active participation in the consortium. It has not functioned just as a ‘buying group’ but as a community initiative and has been vital in encouraging funders and publishers to interact and engage with the UK research management sector.

It would make sense to extend this successful consortium to embrace more PID types. Using the existing Jisc cost-recovery model would provide equality of access, via Jisc’s widely accepted banding mechanisms and support the creation of a group of PID specialists to serve as a national resource. Together, Jisc, funders, and consortium members can advocate for enhancements to shared infrastructures, using the community voice to push those changes forward. In effect, this group could serve as an ‘open infrastructure’ consortium. It would operate as an open social infrastructure in itself, but also support the use of open PID infrastructures wherever the community finds a need.

A UK national PID consortium for higher education institutions and research institutes (potentially including the NHS and other public sector research clusters) could operate with the UK’s research funders and Jisc acting as convenors. Given that open access workflows are a relatively well analysed set of challenges, it could focus on the priority PIDs that have already been identified, with a remit to maintain a manageable portfolio of PIDs in the service of open research.”

⁵ Brown, Josh (2020) Developing a persistent identifier roadmap for open access to UK research. Available at: <http://repository.jisc.ac.uk/7840/>

Appendix 2: How to read the business model canvas

The Business Model Canvas is typically broken down into nine sections (see Figure 1 below). Each section corresponds to a critical aspect of the business model.

Figure 1: A business model canvas

Key partners	Key activities	Value propositions	Customer relationships	Customer segments
	Key resources		Channels	
Cost structure			Revenue streams	

The sections of the canvas can be grouped into three main categories. Figure 2 (below) highlights the external or customer-facing sections of the canvas.

Figure 2: External or customer-facing sections

Key partners	Key activities	Value propositions	Customer relationships	Customer segments
	Key resources		Channels	
Cost structure			Revenue streams	

The component sections of this category are:

- **Customer segments** - this is a list of distinct groupings of customers, classified as high-level types. These ‘segments’ each correspond to a value proposition.
- **Customer relationships** - this is a list of the mechanisms needed to interact with the customers across all segments.
- **Channels** - this is how the business offer will be delivered to the customer.
- **Value propositions** - these are the central motivations driving each customer segment to a product, service, or activity.

The value propositions are central to the business model canvas. They enable us to define the needs of each customer segment at the simplest possible level. Analysing the practical steps necessary to deliver these value propositions helps us to describe what operations must be undertaken by the business if it is to meet customer needs. These internal or operational requirements are set out in the second category, highlighted in Figure 3 (below).

Figure 3: Internal and operational sections

Key partners	Key activities	Value propositions	Customer relationships	Customer segments
	Key resources		Channels	
Cost structure			Revenue streams	

The component sections of this second category are:

- **Key activities** - what are the essential activities that must be undertaken to deliver the value proposition(s)?
- **Key resources** - what resources are needed to operationalise the key activities?
- **Key partners** - which external stakeholders do we need to help us to reach our customers and meet their needs?

Note that there can be overlaps between 'key partners' and 'customer segments'. Co-design is one example of a customer relationship built on partnering.

These activities and resources then enable us to identify the overheads and outgoings associated with business delivery, and to establish what level of income would be needed to sustain the operation. These are the basis for the third category, highlighted in Figure 4 (below).

Figure 4: Financial sections

Key partners	Key activities	Value propositions	Customer relationships	Customer segments
	Key resources		Channels	
Cost structure			Revenue streams	

The component sections of this category are:

- **Cost structure** - this is a list of the key cost areas (staffing for primary areas, technical infrastructure, etc.) associated with delivering the key activities.
- **Revenue streams** - these are all the ways that the delivery of key activities and the value propositions can be monetised to sustain the business.

Cost structures and revenue streams are an integral part of the canvas, but at this stage we are seeking to evaluate the viability of the value proposition for the consortium, not to undertake detailed financial modelling. This will be the next step if the value proposition(s)

are deemed worthwhile, and the consortium approach is selected as a suitable means of delivering them. As well as the financial modelling, other associated research activities, for example ‘willingness to pay’ or market sizing studies, would be needed as part of the next step towards establishing any consortium.

We have made one modification to the standard Business Model Canvas. In response to discussion in the task group’s first meeting, we have sought to capture some of the nuances and priorities specific to each stakeholder group. Since these represent variations in how the value proposition is realised, rather than distinct value propositions in themselves, we have extended the standard Canvas by adding a new section: ‘Critical use cases’ (see Figure 5 below). We did this to record these use cases in context, without losing the clarity the Canvas is designed to bring.

Figure 5: The modified PID consortium business model canvas

Key partners	Key activities	Value propositions	Critical use cases	Customer relationships	Customer segments
	Key resources			Channels	
Cost structure			Revenue streams		